

THE PROBLEM OF DEATH AND IMMORTALITY IN M. BULGAKOV'S NOVEL "THE MASTER AND MARGARITA"

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the philosophical study of the problem of death and immortality in M. Bulgakov's novel "The Master and Margarita". There is a misconception that M. Bulgakov is a Russian writer. This is not a true statement. M. Bulgakov is a Ukrainian philosopher and writer whose works contain philosophical and unique ideas. Today's Ukrainian society, in connection with Russian military aggression, has plunged into the problem of death and immortality of personality as never before since independence. According to the author, the problem of death and immortality is most profoundly revealed in Bulgakov's novel "The Master and Margarita". Ukrainians should not give this genius masterpiece to the Russians. "The Master and Margarita" is a masterpiece of Ukrainian literature written by the Ukrainian writer M. Bulgakov. All Ukrainians must protect the creative heritage of Ukrainian writers, such as M. Bulgakov, from rashists and not give M. Gogol, M. Bulgakov and others Ukrainian authors. The problem of death and immortality in M. Bulgakov's novel "The Master and Margarita" has the complex character of N. Khamitov's meta-anthropological reality and is a system of three dimensions of existence: the everyday Guna dimension, the limiting Sattva dimension, and the meta-limiting dimension of Logos.

Keywords: death, immortality, personality, M. Bulgakov, The Master and Margarita.

Introduction. There is a misconception that M. Bulgakov is a Russian writer. This is not a true statement. M. Bulgakov is a Ukrainian philosopher and writer whose works contain philosophical and unique ideas.

For example, in an interview with O. Barsukova, literary critic R. Semkin says that "Bulgakov cannot be considered a Ukrainian writer" [1].

We cannot agree with R. Semkin. First of all, it is his biography that makes M. Bulgakov Ukrainian. According to researcher N. Yevstafieva, Mykhailo Bulgakov "was born on May 3 (15), 1891 in the family of a teacher of the Kyiv Theological Academy O. I. Bulgakov. His mother – V. M. Bulgakova (maiden name - Pokrovska). The place of birth of the future writer is the house of the priest Father Matvyi Butovsky, who lived in Kyiv on Vozdvizhenska Street, 28. On May 18, the newborn was baptized according to the Orthodox rite in the Ascension Church in Podil" [2, c. 3]. So, if M. Bulgakov was born in Kyiv, then this is already one of the important evidences that M. Bulgakov is a Ukrainian and a Ukrainian writer.

Today's Ukrainian society, in connection with Russian military aggression, has plunged into the problem of death and immortality of personality as never before since independence. We are convinced that the most profound problem of death and immortality is revealed in M. Bulgakov's philosophical novel "The Master and Margarita".

We should not give this genius masterpiece to the Russians. "The Master and Margarita" is a masterpiece of Ukrainian literature written by the Ukrainian writer M. Bulgakov. We must protect the creative heritage of Ukrainian writers, such as M. Bulgakov, from rashists and not give M. Gogol, M. Bulgakov and other Ukrainian authors to the Russians.

Analysis of recent researchers and publications. The problem of death and immortality has already received comprehensive coverage in publications

in modern Ukrainian philosophy. Among the most famous Ukrainian philosophers who research this issue, we can single out the names of N. Khamitov, S. Krylova, P. Nesterenko, T. Kusherets, O. Tytarenko, O. Dobrodum, and others.

Among the newest publications of 2023, we can single out articles by O. Tytarenko, T. Kusherets, and O. Dobrodum.

1. O. Tytarenko "The Problem of Death and Immortality in the Story "May Night or Drowned" by M. Gogol" [5].

Kyiv researcher O. Tytarenko proves that M. Gogol is a Ukrainian philosopher who raises the issue of death and immortality of the individual in his creative works. M. Gogol is a genius of Ukrainian literature [5].

2. T. Kusherets "The Problem of Death and Immortality of Personality in the Poem "Kateryna" by Taras Shevchenko" [4].

The Nizhyn philosopher T. Kusherets investigates the problem of suicide in Ukrainian literature using the example of T. Shevchenko's poem "Kateryna". The author comes to the conclusion that "Kateryna could go to a nunnery, become a mercenary or beg, most importantly – raise her own child. But she chose suicide, which may indicate that Kateryna as a person was broken and could not survive the socially determined psychotrauma of being kicked out of the house by her parents, the wanderings and betrayal and deception she suffered from her beloved Muscovite Ivan" [4].

3. O. Dobrodum "The Problem of Death and Immortality in M. Gogol's Story "The Lost Letter" [3].

Ukrainian researcher O. Dobrodum analyzes the problem of hell in "The Lost Letter" by M. Gogol as a metaphysical problem and proves that hell, in the terminology of N. Khamitov, has an everyday, boundary and meta-boundary existence [3].

Goal. The purpose of this philosophical study is to analyze the problem of death and immortality in M. Bulgakov's novel "The Master and Margarita".

Methods. A philosophical tradition has developed in Kyiv – the Ukrainian meta-anthropology paradigm of N. Khamitov [6], which Ukrainian philosophers use for scientific research in the field of philosophy.

According to Khamitov's Kyiv paradigm, any philosophical phenomena and the behavior and psychology of the literary heroes of the works are analyzed in their everyday, boundary and meta-boundary being [6].

In this study, we will also use the Kyiv paradigm of Ukrainian philosophy for the philosophical analysis of the problem of death and immortality in “The Master and Margarita” by M. Bulgakov.

We also use such classic methods as analysis, synthesis and generalization.

Results. The problem of death and immortality is raised in “The Master and Margarita” from the fact that Berlioz and Woland discuss the existence of God. Berlioz proves that God does not exist and man manages his own life. Woland objects to him and says: “Let me ask you, how can a person lead when he is not only unable to make any plan for at least a ridiculously short term, well, years, say, for a thousand, but also cannot guarantee even for your tomorrow? ... imagine that you, for example, start to manage and order both others and yourself, in general, so to speak, you diverge, and suddenly you have... heh... heh... lung sarcoma... ... and that's the end of your ordering! No one's fate, except your own, bypasses you anymore. Relatives start lying to you. Sensing danger, you rush after learned doctors, then after charlatans, and sometimes even after fortune-tellers. That both the first, and the second, and the third are completely meaningless, you yourself understand. And all this ends tragically: the one who, until recently, thought that he was doing something, suddenly lies motionless in a wooden box, and those around him see that there is no more benefit from such lying, they burn him in the oven” [2, p. 28-29].

Woland goes on to say that another key human affliction is that man is “suddenly mortal” and can die unexpectedly [2, p. 29].

The motif of immortality is raised by M. Bulgakov for the first time in Pilate's conversation with Yeshua, after all, Pilate wants to save Yeshua, but he cannot do it, because the Sanhedrin of scribes and Pharisees choose a thief and a murderer instead of the Messiah and demand to crucify the innocent Yeshua [2].

Berlioz dies an unexpected death. And the death of the Master and Margarita is symbolism. In earthly reality, according to N. Khamitov's meta-anthropology, there are three dimensions [6], but we are convinced that M. Bulgakov in “The Master and Margarita” discovers five dimensions: the dimension of the living, the dimension of the dead, the dimension of supernatural beings, the dimension of death and the dimension of immortality.

When analyzing the problem of death and immortality in “The Master and Marguerite”, an idea arises, and maybe this novel is an illustration for a textbook on psychiatry? Perhaps the entire plot of the novel is a delusion and hallucination? These are philosophical questions to which there is no unequivocal answer.

Let us consider in more detail these five philosophical dimensions of the problem of death and immortality in Bulgakov's “The Master and Margarita”.

1. The dimension of the living. This includes all the heroes of “The Master and Margarita” alive in earthly reality, who were born by humans. According to N. Yevstafieva, “Mikhail Bulgakov began writing the novel “The Master and Margarita” in 1928 or 1929. Neither the Master nor Margarita were among the actors in the first edition. At the beginning of 1930, Bulgakov burned his unfinished novel. In the autumn of 1932, the writer returned to work on the main work of his life. The author's editing of the novel continues with breaks until the last days. The novel has become a classic of world literature, with multi-million copies in our country and abroad. It has been translated into many European, American, and Asian languages, staged and screened many times. Musical works, operas and ballets were created on his plot. The triumphal march of the immortal satirical phantasmagoria-extravaganza with the ingenious insertion of a novel about Christ and Pilate continues” [2].

So, this novel was originally about the world of the living, but over time M. Bulgakov began to develop other dimensions and introduced the main characters – the Master and Margarita – into his novel.

2. The dimension of the dead. This includes all the dead who come to life for a while in the novel. The dimension of the dead is best reflected in Satan's ball.

“At that moment, something brazenly rattled below in the huge fireplace, and some gallows jumped out of it, on which half-burnt ashes were floating. This ash broke from the rope, rattled on the floor, and a black-haired handsome man in a tailcoat and patent leather shoes jumped out of it. A small, half-decomposed coffin ran out of the fireplace, its lid popped off, and more ashes fell from it. The handsome man gallantly jumped up to him and put his hand in a curl, and this second ashes formed into a naked woman in black shoes. ...

One by one, three dominoes fell from the fireplace, cracking and disintegrating, then someone in a black cloak, who was plunged into the back with a knife by the next arrival from the dark mouth. A shrill cry came from below. Next, an almost completely decomposed corpse ran out of the fireplace” [2, p. 276-277]. – talks about the dimension of the dead M. Bulgakov, who were resurrected for a while and came to Satan's Great Ball.

3. The dimension of supernatural beings. This level includes Woland and his helper demons. All supernatural beings in “The Master and Margarita” by M. Bulgakov, light and dark, belong to this dimension of existence.

4. The dimension of death. Death in novel “The Master and Margarita” acts as an invisible force that can come unexpectedly, as it came to Berlioz, and take human life. The dimension of death remains a mystery, a strange transition between earthly and metaphysical realities, which M. Bulgakov depicted in his novel.

5. The dimension of immortality. This level is revealed in the life after the death of both the Master and Margarita, as well as other heroes of the novel who

have gone to extraterrestrial life. "The Master and Margarita" by M. Bulgakov gives faith and hope that the immortality of every person is a possible reality.

This is confirmed by M. Bulgakov with Margarita's final words to the Master in terms of immortality: "Listen to the silence," said Margarita to the Master, and the sand crumbled under her bare feet, "listen and take comfort in what you were not given in life – silence. Look, it is ahead of you, your eternal home, with which you have been rewarded. I can already see the Venetian window and the twisted grapes, they have reached the very roof. This is your home, your eternal home. I know that in the evening those whom you love, to whom your soul lies and who will not upset your balance, will come to you. They will play for you, they will sing to you, you will see the light in the room when the candles are burning. You will fall asleep with your worn and eternal cap on, you will fall asleep with a smile on your face. Sleep will strengthen you, you will get used to thinking wisely. And you won't be able to drive me away. I will take care of your sleep" [2, p. 394].

Discussion. The problem of death and immortality in M. Bulgakov's novel "The Master and Margarita" has the complex character of N. Khamitov's meta-anthropological reality and is a system of three dimensions of existence: the everyday Guna dimension, the limiting Sattva dimension, and the meta-limiting dimension of Logos.

From the dimension of irrationality, Satan, in the form of Woland, enters the mundaneness of the Guna dimension, and the Master and Margarita, being people of the Sattva dimension, at the end of the novel, move into the metaboundary dimension of the Logos after their biological death.

Death and immortality are one of the main motifs of "The Master and Margarita". And, therefore, the problem of death and immortality should continue to be explored in this novel by M. Bulgakov.

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